

Research Article

Development of Fisheries Sector in Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

The 974 km long coastline of Andhra Pradesh, 33,327 square kilometres of continental shelf and about 6 lakh hectares of fresh and brackish water resources provide ample opportunities for a thriving fisheries sector. The sector directly or indirectly provides employment to nearly 1.4 million people and is an important source of foreign exchange earnings. The importance of the segment is evident from the fact that fisheries contributed nearly 5.4 percent to the gross value added of the State in 2015-16. After witnessing a decline of 1.5 percent in 2011-12, the output from fisheries sector registered double digit growth rates in the following three years. The production of brackish water shrimp has witnessed the maximum vibrancy during the subsequent years. Andhra Pradesh shipped 2,83,224.9 MT of sea food worth ₹18,073 crore (US\$2,284.46 million) during 2022-23 and it has contributed 16.32 per cent of sea food exported through ports and air cargo by Marine Products Export Development Authority (MPEDA). The main objective of this paper is to explore the possibility of further improvement in exportable capacity of marine fisheries from the state of Andhra Pradesh including the existing infrastructure and marketing facilities.

Keywords: Fisheries, infrastructure, marketing, welfare programmes and prospects.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The New Sunrise State of Andhra Pradesh is located between 12°41' and 19.07°N latitude and 77° and 84°40'E longitude, and is bordered by Telangana, Chhattisgarh, and Orissa in the north, the Bay of Bengal in the East, Tamil Nadu to the south and Karnataka to the west. Among the other maritime states of India, Andhra Pradesh state is endowed with a long coast line of 974 Kms with a continental shelf area of 33,227 Sq. kms. As per CMFRI census, 2010, the marine fishermen population in 9 coastal districts of Andhra Pradesh estimated at 6.05 lakh with 1.63 lakh fishermen families and 1.51 lakh active fishermen. There are 546 marine fishing villages situated along the coast of Andhra Pradesh. There are about 555 fishermen villages and 349 fish landing centres scattered in 9 coastal districts. A total number of 31,318 fishing vessels comprising 1871 mechanised, 14,648 motorised and 14,799 traditional fishing craft are involved in marine fishing activity. Fishermen are using some principle nets such as Drag nets, gill nets, trawl nets, cast nets, Hook & Line etc. for fishing operations in marine waters.

The contribution of fisheries sector to AP's GSDP is 6.04 %. The overall fish production has more than doubled in the past one decade from 8.14 lakh tons in 2005-06 to 27.66 lakh M.T. in 2016-17. During 2009-10, the total value of marine exports from Andhra Pradesh was Rs. 2,100 crores, which is 20% share in total Indian sea food exports and enhanced to about Rs.

17000 crores during 2016-17. The sector has enormous potential for further enhancement of both productivity and production to achieve 42 lakh tonnes valued @ Rs. 80,000 crores by 2019-10. The sector is providing employment opportunities to nearly 14.5 lakhs people directly and indirectly. Fishers of 2,52,178 were organised into 2275 Fishermen cooperative societies for whom Government is extending many incentives besides providing infrastructure facilities for the socio-economic empowerment.

One major fishing harbour at Visakhapatnam, three minor fishing harbours at Kakinada, Machilipatnam and Nizampatnam are providing berthing facilities for 1871 mechanised fishing vessels in the state. Recognising the importance of fisheries sector, the AP Govt. has identified the Fisheries sector as one of the Growth Engines among 7 missions under Primary Sector for socio-economic development of the new State of Andhra Pradesh.

2. STRATEGIES ADOPTED FOR PROMOTION OF FISHERIES SECTOR:

State is strictly implementing fishing closed seasons in reservoirs and rivers from 1st July to 31st August and Ban period on marine fishing from April 15th to June 14th during every year for conservation and sustainability of the natural fishery resources. African catfish culture was banned with a concern to conserve the native species and protect the biodiversity. Promoting aquaculture with diversified species like GIFT Tilapia, Pangasius, Mud crab, Seabass, and Indian Pompano. Declared Aquaculture Zones in all 9 coastal districts and notified potential area for expansion of the aquaculture. Support for Ease of Doing Business through Online services for issuance of Licenses/ Endorsements for aquaculture farms and aquaculture business operations within prescribed time limit. Providing power tariff concession and supplying quality power to aquaculture farms for 24x7 to facilitate the aquaculture farmers to reduce their production cost and produce healthy crops. Strictly banned usage of antibiotics in aquaculture and enforcing effectively through District Level Taskforce teams. Regularising the aquaculture activities under AP State Aquaculture Development Authority (APSADA), Act, 2020 and ensuring production and supply of quality aquaculture inputs like seed, feed, and feed supplements as per legal provisions made under AP Fish Feed (Quality Control) Act, 2020 and AP Aquaculture Seed (Quality Control) Act, 2020. Promoting domestic marketing through Hub-Spoke model across the state is to enhance per capita fish consumption under the brand of "Fish Andhra- Fit Andhra" programme.

2.1. WELFARE PROGRAMMES:

State in coordination with funding agencies of Govt. of India and External Aided Projects, NABARD etc., has been implementing various welfare schemes for the benefit of fishers, farmers and other stakeholders which mainly includes "Rebate on Diesel" for marine fishing boats, relief to coastal fishers during ban on marine fishing, revolving fund assistance to fisherwomen cooperatives, ex-gratia to deceased fishermen families, power tariff to aquaculture farmers, fishing and aquaculture inputs under PMMSY and other GOI schemes, issuance of Kisan Credit Card (KCC), assistance to fishers and entrepreneurs for establishment of marketing outlets, stocking of quality fish seed in public water bodies, etc.

2.2. INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS:

To address the critical gaps, the State is focusing on establishment of necessary infrastructure in both, capture fisheries and aquaculture sector which mainly includes:

1. Establishment of 2 new fishing harbours, one at Juvvaladinne of Nellore District, another at Uppada of East Godavari District and Upgradation of existing 2 fishing harbours at Machilipatnam and Nizampatnam under Phase-I with total project cost of Rs. 1510

Crore. In Phase-II another five new Fishing harbours are planned for establishment at Budagatlapalem (Srikakulam), Pudimadaka (Visakhapatnam), Biyyaputippa (West Godavari), Vodarevu (Prakasam) Kothapatnam (Prakasam) with a project cost of Rs. 2000 crore with all facilities on par with international standards with funding support from FIDF, PMMSY, NABARD and State funds.

2. Establishment of Aquatic Quarantine Facility (AQF) Centre for *L. vannamei* in Visakhapatnam District to facilitate shrimp hatchery operators to quarantine their imported brood stock and hatcheries for seabass and mud crab in Guntur District with a total project cost of Rs. 75 Crore for production and supply of quality seed for promotion of alternate species culture with funding support from RKVY, State funds.
3. AP has well established aquaculture labs for testing, besides existing 225 labs, the Government is establishing integrated aquaculture labs at 35 locations in 9 coastal districts with all aquaculture input testing facilities with an estimated project cost of Rs. 50 Crore with funding support from RKVY, NABARD and State funds.
4. Establishing 70 Aqua hubs and about 14,000 units of retail outlets for the promotion of domestic marketing under the brand of "Fish Andhra- Fit Andhra" with a total project cost of Rs. 558 Crore across the state with funding support from PMMSY and State funds.

3. TRENDS IN MARINE FISH PRODUCTION:

The marine fish and shrimp production from 2008-09 to 2017-18 reveals that there is a great fluctuation in the catches with a limited growth rate except in 2011-12 (Table-1). Significant growth rate has been witnessed in total production of fish and shrimp in the year 2017-18. The marine production from the inshore waters has reached its optimum and even in case of some species it is over exploited. Further increase in the production from marine sector can be achieved only through judicious management of inshore fishery resources, through proper utilisation of harvested product by increasing shore based facilities, implementation of Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries (CCRF), Monitoring Control and surveillance (MCS) and participatory management and by diversifying to offshore (deep sea) fishing operations like tuna Fishing. The Department has prescribed quality standards of aquaculture seed of all commercial species and enforcing as per the provisions made under AP Aquaculture Seed (Quality Control) (Amendment) Act, 2020. The government has extended seed quality testing facilities and disease diagnosis facilities through Departmental Regional and State Level Aqua labs across all the coastal districts.

Table-1
Marine Fish and Shrimp Production during Last Ten Years: (Lakh Tonnes)

Year	Fish	Shrimp	Total Production	Growth Rate (%)
2008-09	2.45	0.46	2.91	14.12
2009-10	2.46	0.46	2.92	0.34
2010-11	2.52	0.39	2.91	-0.34
2011-12	3.26	0.53	3.79	30.24
2012-13	3.52	0.63	4.15	9.50
2013-14	3.73	0.65	4.38	5.54
2014-15	4.06	0.69	4.75	8.45
2015-16	4.37	0.83	5.20	9.47
2016-17	4.72	1.09	5.81	11.1
2017-18	4.74	1.15	7.04	12.1

Source: Fisheries Statistics, Andhra Pradesh Mannuel.

4. INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITIES AVAILABLE IN MARINE FISHERIES SECTOR:

The following infrastructure facilities are available in Andhra Pradesh state in marine fisheries sector. It revealed that there is significant number of ice plants, Shrimp hatcheries, fish drying platforms and aqua labs for aquaculture.

Table-2

Fishing harbours	4
Shore based facilities	18
Fish drying platforms	174
Shore stations	13
Boat yards	32
Ice plants	235
Cold storages	29
Freezing plants	45
Curing yards	31
Peeling sheds	38
Processing plants	55
Shrimp Hatcheries	292
Feed Mills for aquaculture	28
Aqua labs for aquaculture	160
Fish Landing Centres developed	18

Source: Fisheries Statistics, Andhra Pradesh Mannuel.

The marine products export figures up to December 2021 gives much delight, as the figures registering nearly 35% increase compared to the same period in the last financial year. Interestingly, the export figures up to the third quarter of the current year have surpassed those for the entire Financial Year 2020-21. With marine products export crossing US\$ 6.11 billion, hopes are high that the target of US\$ 7.81 billion set for the current year will be fulfilled. Bhimavaram has emerged as the hub of aquaculture production and processing in Andhra Pradesh and houses 42 seafood processing units. Around 64 exporters are registered with the MPEDA Sub Regional Division at Bhimavaram. MPEDA also has a Quality Control –cum- ELISA Lab at Bhimavaram, which handles over 3500 samples for testing various parameters. The Lab is EIC approved and accredited by NABL as per ISO 17025:2017. There has been a long standing demand from the stakeholders to house the MPEDA office and QC lab in Bhimavaram together. The Andhra Pradesh Agricultural Market Committee has graciously allotted 60 cents of vacant plot to MPEDA inside the Agricultural Market Complex in Bhimavaram. The establishment of the integrated complex will be helpful for both exporters and farmers in getting the services from MPEDA under one roof.

At times, people face major bottlenecks in their day-to-day life due to certain minor gaps in the system or infrastructure. The farmers of Uppigeda creek in Srikakulam district of Andhra Pradesh were facing a similar problem in logistics. There are 8 farmers’ societies registered with NaCSA in the village of which four societies are belonging to the Scheduled Caste. Lack of conveyances across the creek had made it difficult for farmers to source seed, feed and other inputs for aquaculture at an affordable cost. The increase in expenses eroded their feeble profit margin, as they had to make an additional travel of around 20 Kms for transporting goods and crops. At this juncture, MPEDA society, National Centre for Sustainable Aquaculture (NaCSA) got in touch with them and understood their needs.

MPEDA along with the District Administration has decided to construct a cross bridge for the village in Uppigeda creek, which would help the farmers of the village to easily transport aquaculture inputs and take out the harvested crop across the creek saving a lot of time, effort and money. The foundation stone of the cross over bridge in Srikakulam was laid on 30th December 2021. The project costs Rs.250 Lakh, of which 75% will be from MPEDA under the Central Government assistance scheme for the welfare of Scheduled Castes & Scheduled Tribes, and the balance will be borne by the District Administration. During the month, MPEDA has organised three Virtual Buyer Seller meets with the buyers from Russia, China and UAE. In addition, a Business Meet with Kuwait and a preliminary business meet with Denmark were also organised with the help of Indian Missions there.

5. MARINE FISHERY RESOURCE:

Andhra Pradesh is endowed with considerable marine fishery resources. The state has a coast line of 974 km., along the Bay of Bengal. The bottom of the shelf is mostly sandy and muddy, except for a few places of rocky ground. Rich fishing grounds are believed to exist in the offshore waters. Important varieties of marine fishes in the state are sardines, sciannids, ribbon fish, clupeids, pomfret, seer fish, perches leiognathus, elasmobranches, cat fishes, anchovilla and penacid and non-penacid prawns. Seasonal climatic and oceanographic variations are determined by the two monsoon periods (The South West Monsoon April - September and the North - East Monsoon October - March), which largely influence the fisheries. Unlike the situation on the west coast, the South - West Monsoon does not render marine fishing completely impossible since the monsoon here only reflects in the form of cyclonic spells lasting for 3 to 4 days.

The peak season for fishing is from October to April, when 59 percent of the total annual marine catch is landed. May to September is the lean period. except for cyclonic spells, fishing can be conducted at varying degrees throughout the year. The shallow waters less than 40 meters depth are intensively fished all along the coastal line. The concentration of fishing effort on prawn fishing has resulted in some of the other inshore stocks being under exploited or unexplored. As per the Report of the National Commission on Agriculture, 2016, the estimated potential yield for the Andhra Pradesh fisheries is 983756 tones. This estimate was based on production records from 2016. There are 555 Marine Fishing Villages in 65 Mandals and 353 Marine fish landing centres. There are 301956 Marine fishermen. Out of whom 150868 are active fishermen who are actually engaged in the exploitation of marine fishing resources in Andhra Pradesh as per the survey conducted by the Department of Fisheries, Government of Andhra Pradesh during 2010 .There are formal landing facilities for mechanised boats at Visakhapatnam, Kakinada and Nizampatnam.

6. DISTRIBUTION AND MARKETING:

It is estimated that about 40 percent of the marine catch is consumed fresh and the bulk of the balance dried or salted. About 60 percent of the people in Andhra Pradesh are fish eaters. At present the national fish consumption is 11 kgs and in AP, it is estimated at 7.4 kgs. The world fish consumption is 21 kgs. Hence, there is a huge gap in consumption which can be filled up by A.P by promoting domestic market. The existing marketing system involves both public and private sectors. Andhra Pradesh Fisheries Corporation (A.P.F.C) represents the public sector in the marketing system. It has marketing units in coastal districts with fish and prawn procurement centres along the coast to procure fish and prawn directly from the small scale fishermen. The aim is to offer the fishermen a reasonable price for their catch so that they are not exploited by middle-men.

The private sector has the major share of fish marketing. A large number of private traders, small and big, handle the marketing in a complex labour intensive operation. There is generally a large gap between the price paid by the consumers and the price paid to the fishermen. Dried fish is distributed to both coastal and internal district markets. A quantity of 58730 tonnes of fish valued at Rs.72166.50 lakhs and 10045 tonnes of prawn valued at Rs.21094.50 lakhs was exported from Nellore district to other neighbouring states, and 33046.17 tonnes of marine products have been exported to various foreign countries, valued at Rs.29273.20 lakhs during the year 2015-16. The states fish exports in 2013-14 amounted to nearly 5.98 percent and 60.23 percent respectively of the total quantity and value of marine products exported from India. Table-3 presents the value and quantity of fish exported from Andhra Pradesh.

Table-3
Value and Quantity of Fish Exports

Year	Quantity in tonnes	% of total exports from India	Value in Crores (Rs.)	% of total exports from India
2009-10	6,78,436	12.54	10,048.53	16.74
2010-11	8,13,091	19.84	12,901.46	28.39
2011-12	8,62,021	6.02	16,597.23	28.65
2012-13	9,28,215	7.68	18,856.26	13.61
2013-14	9,83,756	5.98	30,213.26	60.23
2014-15	10,51,243	5.24	33,441.61	10.69
2015-16	9,45,892	4.96	30,420.83	-9.03
2016-17	9,55,432	6.22	32,320.55	10.20
2017-18	10,82,321	7.12	33,252.46	11.35
2018-19	11,85,621	8.35	34,821.64	12.52

Source: Marine products exports development Agency (MPEDA)

In the year 2018-19 the exports are increased with 8.35 percent in quantity and 12.52 percent in value. But in the year 2018-19 exports are decreased to 4.96 percent in quantity and -9.03 percent in value. There is a non-uniform trend both in quantity and value of fish exports from the state. Frozen shrimp constitute the bulk of the products exported. The entire export is handled through Chennai and Visakhapatnam port.

7. POLICY MEASURES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FISHERIES SECTOR:

AP Government has been enforcing several Acts and Policies for the sustainability of fisheries and aquaculture sector in the State which includes:

- AP State Aquaculture Development Authority (APSADA) Act, 2020, for regulation, monitoring, and development of the aquaculture sector in the State through AP State Aquaculture Development Authority under the Chairmanship of Hon'ble Chief Minister, Govt. of AP
- A.P. Feed (Quality Control) Act, 2020 to ensure production and supply of quality and antibiotic free aquaculture feeds on par with BIS/FAO Standards
- A.P. Aquaculture Seed (Quality Control) (Amendment) Act, 2020 for production and supply of quality and antibiotic free aquaculture seed to aqua farmers in the State
- Ensuring Coastal security through Registration of marine fishing vessels under APMFR Act, 1994 & MS Act, 1958, implementation of colour code and issuance of QR based Aadhaar cards to coastal fishers

- Ban on usage of antibiotics in aquaculture through District Level Task force teams and regular inspection of hatcheries, aqua farms, aqua input shops for collection of samples for testing for antibiotics with the support of MPEDA (National Residue Control Programme (NRCP), EIA (RASFF) and CAA.
- Ban on usage of poultry litter, poultry offal and slaughter wastages in aquaculture for curtailing the transmission of antibiotics and to regulate the environmental pollution.
- Aquaculture Zonation for regulating the unauthorised conversion of agriculture lands to aquaculture and promotion of area expansion in potential areas which are saline, low productive, barren, inundated land which are not fit for the agriculture.
- Extension of services through Rhythu Bharosa Kendra's (RBK's) to fishers and aqua farmers at village level through Village Fisheries Assistants (VFA's) which includes:
 - Facilitating for issuance of Kishan Credit Card (KCC) to fishers and farmers
 - E-crop booking: Updating aquaculture area with crop details for facilitating the farmers to get remunerative price for their aqua produce
 - Technical support to fishers and farmers at field level through Matsya Sagu Badi (MSB) programmes
 - Supply of quality and certified inputs (fish feeds and feed supplements) to aqua farmers
 - Extending aquaculture input testing facilities to farmers through integrated aquaculture labs.

8. KEY IMPACTS:

Total fish and prawn production has been increased from 39.91 LMT (2018-19) to 46.23 LMT (2020-21) with increase of 16% fish production.

- ❖ Area under aquaculture increased from 1.96 lakh ha (2018-19) to 2.09 lakh ha (2020-21) with 6% increase.
- ❖ Identified and notified 48,778 hectares of potential area for expansion of Aquaculture under Aquaculture Zonation (Freshwater -20,744 ha, brackish water - 28031 ha).
- ❖ Fisheries sector Contribution of GSDP is Rs.77588 Crore out of total GSDP of the State of Rs. 9,86,611 Crore, which is 7.86%.
- ❖ Fisheries sector contribution to State GVA is 8.24 % and 27.91 % to agricultural GVA
- ❖ The livelihood opportunities to rural folk in fisheries and aquaculture sector have been increased from 16.46 lakhs (2019-20) to 20.15 lakhs (2020-21), with increase of 22.4%.

9. CONCLUSION:

India has rich and diverse fisheries resources ranging from deep seas to lakes, ponds, rivers and more than 10% of the global biodiversity in terms of fish and shellfish species. The marine fisheries resources are spread along the country's vast coastline and 2.02 million square km Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and 0.53 million sq.km continental shelf area. Since the sector is extremely diverse and dynamic, the scope of the National Fisheries Policy, 2020 encompasses development, management and regulation of inland and marine fishery resources including aquaculture in marine, freshwater, brackish water and saline/alkaline areas and their post-harvest management, strengthening and modernisation of the value chain. The major strength of the Andhra Pradesh Fisheries sector is the enterprising, innovative and proactive fisheries, the private industry in aquaculture, fishery and associated areas. In spite of positive growth in three sectors of brackish water aquaculture, fish water aquaculture and marine fisheries, there are many constraints and limitations that come in the way of sustainable development fisheries sector of Andhra Pradesh.

As quality of seafood and fishery related traceability and sustainability certifications are major factors for purchase decisions these days, quality testing infrastructure and enforcement of sustainability measures attains utmost importance. The constraints have to be addressed with a systemic approach and the gaps have to be plugged in to enhance our production and processing capabilities. It also requires associated capacity building exercises on quality, traceability and sustainability aspects besides skilling of the farmers and workers to produce quality products that could be promoted under Brand India. There is a huge potential to increase Indian seafood export. However, the continuing Covid – 19 pandemic forces us to revisit the growth of the sector and urge us to place it in a more workable perspective, as all the stakeholders are still reeling under huge turmoil caused by the pandemic situation in export trade. The shortage of containers and the surge in freight charges for exports in 2021 have caught exporters off the guard.

The major strength of the Andhra Pradesh Fisheries sector is the enterprising, innovative and proactive fishers, aqua farmers, the private industry in aquaculture, fishery and associated areas. The major strength of the Andhra Pradesh Fisheries sector is the enterprising, innovative and proactive fishers, aqua farmers, the private industry in aquaculture, fishery and associated areas.

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